

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 7/5-8/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: ≈ 10.65	Bottom: ≈ 10.49
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 19-21 cms	Width:	Length:	Depth: 17 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	CLAY ?	TAN	Very Compact Hard	Fine	T 1	Lm	Gp
					Surface	Gr	Char ✓ Spots - Flecks Throughout
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
		Other					
1a	Gypsum Sand MIX	White (Gypsum) Tan (Sand)	Crumbly	Rubblx	T 0	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
		Other					
2 **	CLAY or SAND - GYPSUM MIX	Light Grey	Packed But Very Soft in Drying	Crumbly to very fine powder- like	T 2	Lm ✓ Frags - small	Gp
						Gr ✓ *	Char ✓ Spots Throughout
						Dolerite ✓ Small Chips	
					D 2 *	Ba	
						Al	
		Other / Small Bone (?) Splinter					
2a **	Fine Gypsum clay - MIX ? Ash ?	white & Yellow Fine Speckled to Grey	Very Soft	Fine Powder like when lumps broken	T 1	Lm ✓ Frags Some	Gp
					2cm diam	Gr ✓ Few Frags	Char ?
						Do	
					D 0	Ba	
						Al	
		Other					
3	SAND	TAN to Brown	Loose	Granular	T 0	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char ✓ Minute Flecks 2-3
						Do (Diorite) Very Small Chip	
					D	Ba Dolerite 2-3 Tiny Particles	
						Al	
		Other					

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 2 28, 36 3 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 12	No. / 3	B&W: Roll/ 2 20, 24, 25, 26, 27 3 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33
------------	--	---------	--

DRAWN	Area Plan: Plotted 1:20 Detail 1:10	Feature Plan: Detail 1:10 w FH15-h16 d8 1:2 Plan Sherd, after @ Removed	Sections: Facing SW, SE
-------	---	--	----------------------------

REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: * Small granite pieces mostly from pocket of granite dust and/or very small frags. just above large sherds in 2

** 2-2a excavated together except for N Quadrant where 2a taken out saved separately - elsewhere mixed in tray

* 2 large diagenetic pieces fit to form side of crude red ware vessel (black at fracture) that seems to fit against N side of FH14 - contours may match Many small pottery chips from 2 large pieces